

Aiming for success: Ireland's new Primary Mathematics Curriculum

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A new curriculum provides an opportunity to propose a fresh new vision for children's learning and refine our understanding of what successful learning looks like. In Ireland, a new Primary Mathematics Curriculum has recently been published that sets forth a new such vision for children's mathematical learning. Tracing the development of the new curriculum, and explicating the rationale for curriculum change and the research base developed, provides an important context for the development of a new Primary Mathematics Curriculum in Ireland. This paper will extract and discuss the core components and features of the new Irish Primary Mathematics Curriculum, and the implications this will have on children's learning experiences and for teaching the curriculum in practice.

Keywords: Curriculum development, primary mathematics, curriculum enactment

Introduction

The National Council for Curriculum and Assessment (NCCA) is a statutory body of the Department of Education comprised twenty-five members appointed by the Minister. The remit of NCCA is to advise the Minister for Education on curriculum and assessment for early childhood education, primary and post-primary schools, as well as assessment procedures used in schools and examinations on subjects which are part of the curriculum.

To develop this advice, NCCA engages in robust discussions and deliberations with Council, its three supporting boards (Early childhood and primary, junior cycle, senior cycle) and the numerous development groups that are tasked with developing individual curriculum specifications and supports. The advice is also shaped by feedback from consultations with the public, schools and early childhood settings, education stakeholders and others.

A new Primary Mathematics Curriculum (DoE, 2023a) has recently been published. This new curriculum holds a new vision for children's learning in mathematics that represents a fresh and innovative conceptualisation of what it means to be 'successful' with mathematics. In this paper, this new vision for children's learning will be outlined in the context of the broader aims and goals of the *Primary Curriculum Framework* (DoE, 2023b). It will then discuss the rationale for curriculum change and describe the journey of curriculum development in the context of primary mathematics. Following this, the research base and core beliefs which underpin the new curriculum will be presented, in addition to the key stated aims of the curriculum. The paper will then detail the key components of the new curriculum specification before discussing key considerations for enacting the new curriculum in practice.

A new vision for children's learning in primary school

In Ireland, the *Primary Curriculum Framework* (DoE, 2023b) sets out a new vision for high-quality and inclusive learning, teaching, and assessment for all children attending primary and special schools. Developed by NCCA, the framework is informed by research, deliberation, and sustained work with school communities; it is the culmination of wide

consultation and collaboration across the system. It aims to provide a strong foundation for every child to thrive and flourish, supporting them in realising their full potential as individuals and as members of communities and society. The curriculum views children as unique, competent and caring individuals, and it views teachers as committed, skilful and agentic professionals.

To achieve this vision, the *Primary Curriculum Framework* (DoE, 2023b) spotlights eight essential broad overarching principles.

Figure 1

Principles of learning, teaching and assessment

As children progress through primary school, it is envisaged that they will develop competencies that allow them to interact and engage with the social world of their home, community and school, and navigate a wide variety of contexts and situations, not only in childhood but as they mature into adolescence and adulthood. The following seven inextricably linked key competencies, closely linked with the four themes of *Aistear: the Early Childhood Curriculum Framework* (NCCA, 2009a), and the eight Key Skills in the *Framework for Junior Cycle* (DES, 2015); encapsulate the essential knowledge, skills, concepts, dispositions, attitudes and values which enable children to adapt to and deal with a range of situations, challenges and contexts.

Figure 2

Seven key competencies

Curriculum change in primary mathematics

The current Primary School Mathematics Curriculum (DES, 1999) is based on constructivist principles and comprises five strands: Number, Algebra, Shape and Space, Measures, and Data, with Early Mathematical Activities an additional strand for junior infants only. Within these strands, the content is delineated by year and is articulated by a large number of learning objectives.

To develop a new Primary Mathematics Curriculum (PMC), a development group was assembled in late 2016 to begin the process of specification development. This group comprises fourteen members including a chair, representatives from a number of nominating organisations and a small number of co-options. The development of the new PMC sought to build on the success of the current 1999 curriculum and Aistear (NCCA, 2009a), and to address issues raised in a number of publications, including curriculum implementation reviews and evaluations (DES, 2005; NCCA, 2005, 2009b; Murchan et al., 2009) and international and national assessments (e.g. Eivers et al., 2010; Mullis et al., 2012; Sheil et al., 2014). The new curriculum also sought to respond to calls from teachers to reduce curriculum overload and allow for greater teacher autonomy and agency in managing teaching and learning in their classrooms (INTO, 2015).

Initially, the remit for the Early Childhood and Primary Mathematics Development Group was the development of a mathematics specification for children from junior infants to second class. This first draft specification (NCCA, 2017) was published for consultation, in late October 2017. Findings from the first consultation included calls to improve the accessibility of language used in the specification, further guidance on the use of Learning Outcomes as a basis for learning, teaching, assessment and preparation. To mitigate concerns about the removal of class-based learning objectives, teachers called for a greater level of

specificity as to the core concepts which underpin each Learning Outcome (NCCA, 2018). This consultation gave rise to a number of new developments, including a revision of Chapter 6, 'Primary Mathematics in Practice', and the development of a suite of Mathematical Concepts and new Support Materials for teachers and parents.

Following this first consultation, the Minister for Education decided that the curriculum should be developed as a full specification from junior infants to sixth class. In 2022, a second consultation was conducted on a full specification of the PMC. Findings from this consultation revealed issues associated with teacher confidence and enacting the new curriculum. Stakeholders called for clearer explanations about the core changes arising in terms of children's learning and pedagogy in working towards this new vision for mathematics learning in primary schools. Additional themes such as alignment, supporting enactment and using Learning Outcomes also featured prominently (NCCA, 2023). Importantly, a key feature of the second consultation involved a greater emphasis on gathering the perspectives of children (Leavy et al., 2023). Amongst a wealth of insights shared by children in the consultation, they called for more collaboration in terms of their mathematics learning, as well as real-world, hands-on and playful learning experiences. Notably, in classes in which 'procedure-focused' and textbook-driven learning dominated, children generally reported negative emotions regarding their mathematical learning experiences. The findings from both the main consultation report (NCCA, 2023) and the report on the findings from children (Leavy et al., 2023) provided useful feedback to help refine the PMC specification and draft support materials; as well as shaping the design of new components of the Primary Mathematics Toolkit.

Research base to support developments

In addition to the consultation reports emerging from these two consultations, a rich research base underpins the development of the new PMC. In line with the two-phase development process described above, the initial research conducted to support developments includes a systematic review of the literature, concentrating on teaching and learning for children aged three to eight years. This includes an international audit of mathematics curriculum policy (Burke, 2014). It also features Research Report 17 which provides the theoretical underpinnings for the development of mathematics education in young people, and discusses current thinking and views on mathematics, specifically regarding definitions, theories, development and progression (Dunphy, et al., 2014). Additionally, Research Report 18 deals with current thinking on the teaching and learning of mathematics, investigating what constitutes good mathematics pedagogy and looks at appropriate structures for the development of mathematical knowledge for pre- and in-service teachers (Dooley et al., 2014). Finally, a background paper and brief for development of the draft PMC (NCCA, 2016) was subsequently produced.

In the second phase of developments, an addendum to Research Reports 17 and 18 (Dooley, 2019) and five short research papers which examined core mathematical concepts, skills and processes with which children engage across the five mathematical domains

(Delaney, 2020; Leavy, 2020; Nic Mhuirí, 2020a, 2020b; Twohill, 2020) were commissioned to complement the existing research base and offer insights on children's mathematical learning in the senior classes of primary school.

Core beliefs underpinning the new Primary Mathematics Curriculum

The new PMC makes explicit a set of core beliefs upon which the curriculum is developed. From the outset, the curriculum asserts that 'every child is mathematical'. As such, every child is considered to have an innate, intuitive and instinctive sense of mathematics which is deepened and developed over time as they engage in rich learning experiences. Accordingly, it acknowledges that a child's mathematical learning journey begins from birth, from which they learn mathematics through their interactions and experiences in their home environment, and later build on this learning through early childhood, primary and post-primary education.

The curriculum also sets out a solid stance on mathematics as a discipline for learning, and the implications this has for the kind of learning experiences that children ought to have in primary school. Mathematics is both a human and social phenomenon that is shaped by their social, cultural and educational experiences. Mathematics is a tool that helps us to make sense of our world so that we can think about, see and organise our everyday lives. Mathematics is also considered to be beautiful and worthy of pursuit and exploration in its own right. Finally, mathematics is everywhere and for everyone.

Given these beliefs, it holds that a child's primary mathematics education ought to tap into their innate ability to think and communicate mathematically. Moreover, it should provide opportunities to allow children to communicate and work collaboratively to co-construct knowledge and skills as they interact and collaborate to solve real-life problems. Rich learning experiences with mathematics should be characterised by playfulness, creativity, modelling, thinking aloud and maths talk. And importantly, children should be encouraged to have a positive disposition towards mathematics and develop their proficiency, confidence and resilience through their learning experiences in primary school.

Aim of curriculum: Mathematical proficiency - A new conceptualisation of success for children

The aim of the PMC represents a new conceptualisation of success for children's learning in mathematics, namely the development of mathematical proficiency. This term aims to capture the complex web of intricate knowledge, skills, abilities, and beliefs that children ought to develop to become more confident and competent mathematical learners (Kilpatrick et al., 2001). There are five aspects to mathematical proficiency, as presented in Figure 3.

Figure 3

Five aspects of mathematical proficiency

When considering mathematical proficiency, it would be incorrect to look at any of these individual strands independently, rather they comprise different parts of a complex whole that are interwoven and interdependent in the development of mathematical proficiency (Kilpatrick et al., 2001). Indeed, each of the five aspects can serve to complement and strengthen each other. For example, as a child develops their procedural fluency and becomes more automatic in applying procedures to solve problems, their strategic competence becomes more efficient and effective, enabling them to tackle increasingly complex and novel problems.

Mathematical proficiency is acquired and deepened over time through engagement with meaningful, sustained, engaging and playful learning experiences where children can problem-solve, practice procedures and skills, interrogate mathematical ideas, reason, argue and make connections with their learning. Such experiences provide the opportunity for all children to develop and achieve proficiency. Indeed, rather than being the gift of ‘more able’ children, the new PMC holds that mathematical proficiency is a necessary and appropriate aim for all children in primary and special schools (NCCA, 2016).

Structure of new curriculum

The new curriculum is structured according to five strands or categories of learning, namely, Algebra, Data and Chance, Measures, Number, and Shape and Space. Each strand has a set of strand units, numbering fourteen in total. Each strand unit has a set of Learning

Outcomes. Within the new PMC, Learning Outcomes are used to describe the expected mathematical learning and development for all learners at the end of a two-year stage, when due consideration is taken of individual abilities and varying circumstances. Learning Outcomes articulate big mathematical ideas, and encompass the knowledge, skills and dispositions that the PMC aspires for children to develop.

Importantly, the curriculum also puts forward Elements which describe the main categories of processes that children engage in through their mathematical learning. These mathematical processes are categorised into four Elements: Understanding and Connecting, Communicating, Reasoning and Applying and Problem-solving. These Elements are central to the development of children’s mathematical proficiency, and involve children connecting, communicating, reasoning, justifying, representing, problem-solving, generalising and argumentation.

Figure 4

The strands and elements of the Primary Mathematics Curriculum

The new curriculum features a chapter ‘Maths curriculum in practice’ that describes the fundamental features of children’s learning with the curriculum and the corresponding pedagogical practices that support and enhance learning. For ‘Learning primary mathematics’, this section outlines the kind of playful and engaging mathematical learning experiences that should be offered to children. These opportunities are categorised according to four

curriculum Elements, as described above. In terms of ‘Teaching primary mathematics’, this section proposes five key practices that are essential to the provision of quality mathematical learning experiences. These practices are described in greater detail in the next section.

Finally, this chapter explores ‘Assessing primary mathematics’ as an integral part of mathematics learning and teaching. It views teachers as committed, skilled and agentic professionals who make key decisions every day about mathematical teaching and learning. These decisions are informed and shaped by the teacher’s knowledge of the child and their prior learning, their knowledge of the curriculum and knowledge of pedagogy.

The PMC specification is accompanied by the Primary Mathematics Toolkit, an online space made up of four key components; mathematical concepts, progression continua, support materials and examples of children’s learning. The Primary Mathematics Toolkit provides practical support for teachers and parents in building rich mathematical learning experiences for children.

Enacting the new curriculum

The curriculum puts forward five key pedagogical approaches, deemed as essential to the provision of quality mathematical learning experiences.

Figure 5

Five key pedagogical practices for the classroom

1. **Fostering productive disposition:** The first approach conveys the important role dispositions play in children’s mathematical learning, highlighting how they can be nurtured or changed over time. It calls on teachers to emphasise the rich, useful and meaningful nature of mathematics in the classroom. The multiple ways in which children engage with mathematics, how they perceive mathematics and the rich

contexts in which mathematics is meaningfully presented to them, are what help form and shape their dispositions towards mathematics.

2. **Encouraging playfulness with mathematics:** Highlighting the role of playful learning for all children across all stages of primary education, this approach provides teachers with an opportunity to engage with children in purposeful and sensitive ways. By infusing playfulness in children's learning experiences, this helps provide an important context for mathematical thinking and the development of mathematical language and concepts.
3. **Emphasising mathematical modelling:** Mathematical modelling involves children using mathematics to understand and describe a problem-context and determine meaningful solutions to problems. It foregrounds the importance of exploration, sense-making, conceptual understanding and flexibility in thinking. Children can be supported to form models through a process of testing, revising and expressing their interpretation of different mathematical ideas, experiences, problems and situations, typically posed to them as questions or challenges.
4. **Using cognitively challenging tasks:** Viewed as rich, higher-order learning opportunities, cognitively challenging tasks can be used to appropriately stretch and challenge children's conceptual understanding as they encounter significant mathematical ideas and situations. Such tasks can provide all children with the opportunity to access mathematics, while offering the potential for deeper engagement.
5. **Promoting maths talk:** Maths talk is a collaborative process where children's thinking, strategies and ideas are expressed, shared and/or exchanged. Providing a space for maths talk allows children to reflect on their own understanding; define, present and justify their ideas; make sense of and critique their own ideas and those of others; and develop their ability to express and articulate their thinking.

While presented separately, these practices are dynamic and naturally link with each other. They foster an inclusive learning environment and culture where children engage in rich and meaningful learning processes.

Practicalities and conclusion

A curriculum change can, for many, necessitate a shift in the role of the teacher and the mindset they hold towards mathematics. Viewing the role adopted by teachers as critical, Dooley and colleagues (2014) highlight how teachers are responsible for structuring the learning environment and developing the learning experiences for children, thus enabling mathematical learning to take place. The authors point out that for many teachers, this will involve embracing pedagogical approaches that will be markedly different from what they experienced as mathematics learners. In working with the new curriculum and embracing the new pedagogical approaches that are outlined above, teachers will be asked to reflect on their own views of mathematics. Teachers will also be challenged to consider the dispositions they themselves hold towards mathematics, their perceptions of 'playfulness' with mathematics and their beliefs about children's innate mathematical abilities. Confronting these considerations will be an important starting point for bringing responsive pedagogical approaches to life in mathematics classrooms and successfully enacting the new curriculum.

Following approval by the Minister of Education, the new PMC is expected to be published in Autumn, 2023. It holds a strong and ambitious vision for children in primary and special schools in Ireland to foster a love for mathematics and to develop as confident and proficient mathematical learners. Following its publication and introduction to schools, teachers, parents and children will have the opportunity to engage in robust conversations about the new curriculum, and to consider how this new vision and conceptualisation of success for children's learning in mathematics will be actualised.

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